

TEACHING DIALOGICAL SPEECH IN SCHOOLCHILDREN OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS.

Abdullayeva Nigora Rakhimovna

Senior lecturer, Kokand State Pedagogical Institute.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11529939>

Abstract. *This article Speech development is a historically established form of human communication through language. Select and characterize methods for determining the level of speech development of older preschool children.*

Keyword: *teacher, game, process, leadership, lesson, training, integration, thinking, creativity, intelligence.*

ОБУЧЕНИЕ ДИАЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ РЕЧИ ШКОЛЬНИКОВ ДОШКОЛЬНЫХ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ УЧРЕЖДЕНИЙ.

Аннотация. *Данная статья Развитие речи является исторически сложившейся формой человеческого общения посредством языка. Выбрать и охарактеризовать методы определения уровня речевого развития детей старшего дошкольного возраста.*

Ключевые слова: *учитель, игра, процесс, лидерство, урок, обучение, интеграция, мышление, творчество, интеллект.*

Dialogue-conversation is the main form of communication of a child with adults and his peers.

In a preschool educational institution, training is carried out in two forms: a) in free speech communication; B) in special training.

Dialogue appears more freely in colloquial communication, and it is the basis of enrichment of children's vocabulary, the natural development of pronunciation-specific, grammatical skills, the basis for acquiring fluent speech skills.

The dialogue is taught in special classes (1-2 sessions per month); during the day in a preschool educational institution, the child enters into free communication with an educator and other children. And at home, adults should engage in dialogue with the child on various topics.

Special classes on the development of dialogic fluent speech are held on the basis of the conversational method (conversation) and The Imitation method. These methods are often carried out using the following methods:

- Preparation conversation (speaking) methods;

- Theatricalization methods (imitation, retelling). The prepared conversation has the following tasks:

- Direct-to talk children, that is, to listen without the words of the interlocutor, to behave in a state of mind without waiting for a favorable moment to throw a bite, to speak intelligibly to the interlocutor;

- Placenta - practice pronunciation and grammatical skills, certain words clarify the meaning.

In the process of conversation, the educator uses various methods, such as questions, riddles, an artistic word. All these methods help to direct the process of mastering knowledge during a conversation, provide speech communication, activate children's thoughts, their attention, memories, emotions. But the leading way to conduct a conversation is questions. The success and pedagogical effectiveness of a conversation with children will largely depend on the correct placement of questions. Knowing how to ask questions and gradually increase the complexity and difficulty of its answer is one of the most basic and necessary pedagogical habits. To put a question means to put in front of children the task of speech thinking at the level that their strength reaches.

At the moment, it should not be made easier, except for Khad, because the purpose of setting such a task is to encourage children to think, remember. Depending on what kind of thinking-speaking tasks it sets, questions can be divided into reproductive, search and problem questions.

In the conversation, it is necessary to draw conclusions about the connection between objects, use the accumulated knowledge, comparisons, and why? Why? Because of what? What are they similar to? Why? How? questions of search and problem tone that require answers to questions such as will be of leading importance.

At each stage of the conversation, it is necessary to place the questions in approximately the following sequence: initially reproductive to animate the children's experience, then a small number of but complex search questions to digest the new material, and at the end 1-2 generalizing questions. Questions should be clear and targeted. Questions that are ambiguous make it difficult for children to answer – they cannot answer or answer incorrectly. The question should be asked clearly, without haste, observing logical accents, meaningful pauses. The caregiver maintains a pause to give the child time to respond. If the question is asked quickly, the child will not have time to understand its content and will have to repeat the question of the educator several times, which will interfere with the child in thinking about the answer, teach him not to listen to the educator. It is necessary to teach the child to take the question the first time.

In the process of interviewing the educator, the following can be done:

* Reciting certain syntactic structures of sentences not mastered by children, consisting of compound sentences or a kind of member;

- To tell the intonation of meaningful fragments of a sentence that children have not mastered (e.g., the intonation, the cheering, the anxiety falling, the intonation of the joy, and x.k;
- To say the formation of one-core words: liquid-liquid, vegetable-vegetable, etc.
- Help in the formation of unstressed verb forms: sprinkle-sprinkled, putty.

In the process of conversation, it is necessary to encourage children to ask questions, develop their curiosity. The child's ability to ask questions is evidenced by his thinking activity.

The method of theatrical production of fiction – fairy tales, stories, poems – is the way in which children retell the works that the educator read to them on behalf of those individuals.

It is better to use works that involve dialogical speech to retell on behalf of other individuals. Retelling them makes it possible to refine children's verbal speech, in particular, the intonations of Appeal, counting, cheering, cheering; speech becomes more emotionally rich – it is caused by the morality of the characters that the gox is happy, the gox is sad, and the gox begunamo sounds.

In the process of teaching children oral dialogical speech, it is recommended to use such methods as theatrical performance, puppet theater. Children can participate in this as both performers and spectators.

A staging game is a game in which children retell a work of art in the images of its characters; children freely retell the text and children's plot-role-playing games.

In plot-role-playing games, children are allowed, first of all, to deviate from the text of the fairy tale in their speech. The educator corrects them only when the grammar or lexicon deviates from the norms of literary colloquial speech; it is not necessary to correct it when phonetic errors are made during the game.

Theatrical performances differ from staging games in that they involve children who know the text of a work of art by heart, the purpose of which is to entertain their listening friends from this performance; in this performance, children come out in theatrical costumes (mask caps and other clothes).

Puppet theater is a plot "directing" of different types of play: children at the same time simple toys (toy theater), parsley (dolls worn on the fingers of the hand, photo clippings and x.k.) while forcing them to play the characters of the work, they speak the text of the work of fiction by role.

Puppet tearty forms include: Toy Theatre, parsley Theatre, fingers Theatre, shadow theatre, table Theatre, flannelegraph.

Children's publishing houses are printing visual guides to folk tales, such as silhouettes; theater-books; panorama-books, for staging works of art.

The types of puppet theater listed above are used in a preschool educational institution as methodological tools for activating children's speech: children are used with the help of an educator, and in large groups they themselves independently direct dolls, shaved pictures, they passionately speak on behalf of them and thus develop their oratory skills.

A staging game is a theatrical performance of any child of preschool age.

Depending on the course of children's mastery of verbal speech skills, their answers to questions should become more clear, thoughtful and meaningful.

The vitality of speech with children in the process of conversation is largely due to the variety of grammatical structures inherent in oral speech and the question and answer form of speech communication.

In conversations, children can give a comprehensive opinion and give an answer that consists of a couple of words (Did you like a fairy tale-Xa.). It is necessary to direct children to comprehensive answers by correctly placing questions: "What is the weather in Bakhor more? Tell in this Haq".

The child can be instructed like this: "give a short answer. Give a detailed answer (but not with a full answer)", which can be asked: "who can give a short answer (or give a more beautiful answer from your comrade)". In the necessary cases, the educator can demonstrate an example of a comprehensive answer to the question posed.

REFERENCES

1. Abdullayeva N. R. et al. Study of Alkylphenol-Formaldehyde Oligomers Modified with Amines Containing Imidazoline Fragments as Corrosion Inhibitors in the Composition of Preservation Fluids.
2. <https://scholar.google.com/scholar?oi=bibs&hl=ru&q=related:gXdc-Kbh4SoJ:scholar.google.com/>
3. Abdullayeva, Nigora, and Sevinch Bahodir qizi Bahodirova. "TALABALARNING KASBIY KOMMUNIKATIV KOMPETENSIYALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH." *ILM FAN TARAQQIYOTIDA ZAMONAVIY METODLARNING QO'LLANILISHI* 3.5 (2023): 11-14.
4. https://scholar.google.com/scholar?oi=bibs&hl=ru&q=related:6DP5L0_O4sgJ:scholar.google.com/

5. Abdullayeva, N. R. (2018). Nitrogen-containing organic compounds as inhibitors of corrosion in an aqueous medium. *Processes of Petrochemistry and Oil Refining*, (3), 282-294.
6. https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=DEaSb2sAAA&AJ&citation_for_view=DEaSb2sAAAAJ:LkGwnXOMwfcC
7. Abdullayeva N. R. MONOALKYL (C8-C12) PHENOLFORMALDEHYDE OLIGOMERS MODIFIED BY IMIDAZOLINES ON THE BASIS OF FATTY ACIDS OF THE VEGETABLE OILS AS A COMPONENT OF THE CONSERVATION LIQUIDS. – 2019.
8. https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=DEaSb2sAAA&AJ&citation_for_view=DEaSb2sAAAAJ:_FxGoFyzp5QC
9. Abdullayeva, N. R., Amiraslanova, M. N., Aliyeva, L. I., Akhmedbekova, S. F., & Rustamov, R. A. (2019). SYNTHESIS AND MODIFICATION OF ALKYL PHENOL-FORMALDEHYDE OLIGOMERS WITH IMIDAZOLINES ON THE BASES OF FATTY ACIDS OF VEGETABLE ORIGIN. *Processes of petrochemistry and oil refining*, 20(1), 25-32.
10. https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=DEaSb2sAAA&AJ&citation_for_view=DEaSb2sAAAAJ:kc_bZDykSOC
11. Abdullayeva, Narmina R., et al. "Imidazolines on the bases of fatty acids of palm oil as modifiers of phenolic oligomers." *Processes of Petrochemistry and Oil Refining* 21.2 (2020): 224-230.
12. https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=DEaSb2sAAA&AJ&citation_for_view=DEaSb2sAAAAJ:4T0pqqG69KYC
13. Xamidovna, Mamayusupova Iroda. "EVACUATION OF THE LEVEL OF CONFLICTS IN CONFLICT SITUATIONS BETWEEN ADOLESCENTS." *Confrencea 1.1* (2023): 23-27. <https://confrencea.org/index.php/confrenceas/article/view/372/375>
14. Khamidovna, Mamayusupova Iroda. "MASTERY OF MANAGING PEDAGOGICAL COMMUNICATION STUDY, GENERALIZATION AND DISSEMINATION OF ADVANCED PEDAGOGICAL EXPERIENCE." *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal* 10.12 (2022): 1217-1222. <https://internationaljournals.co.in/index.php/giirj/article/view/4627/4322>
15. Khamidovna M. I. CAUSES OF FAMILY CONFLICTS //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 10. – №. 12. – С. 870-872. <https://internationaljournals.co.in/index.php/giirj/article/view/3156/2907>

16. Khamidovna, M. I. (2022). The influence of older people on the formation of the spiritual environment in Uzbek families. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(10), 360-364.

https://api.scienceweb.uz/storage/publication_files/3062/8164/641d74df6fdbcb0d098d0bc0bf0b0d184d0b0d0ba0d182d0be0d18074d0a0d0b0d0b2d188d0b0d0bd0d0b6d0be0d0bd29b0d0b8d180d29b0d0b8d0bb0d0b3d0b0d0bd.pdf